

Chemistry of Bis-2'-cyanoethyl Derivatives of Some Aromatic Primary Amines. Part I. Preparation of Some New Tertiary Aminobenzaldehydes and a Study of Some of their Reactions

Abraham Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah

Preparation and properties of bis-2'-cyanoethyl derivatives of some aromatic primary amines are described. Formylation of two bis-cyanoethyl derivatives and a study of the reactions of the aldehydes formed have also been made.

Braunholtz and Mann¹ prepared the dicyanoethyl derivatives of several amines by refluxing a mixture of the amine, acrylonitrile, glacial acetic acid, and freshly prepared cuprous chloride. The same method was used by Ittyerah and Mann² for dicyanoethylation of 3,5-xylylidine. This communication deals with the study of the properties of these dicyanoethyl derivatives. Formylation of two bis-2'-cyanoethyl derivatives (I: R=H or Me) and a study of the reactions of the aldehydes (II: R=H or Me), thus obtained, have been made.

The formyl group can be introduced into an aromatic nucleus by various methods³. Some of the common reagents used for the purpose are formaldehyde, hexamine, *N*-methylformanilide, and dimethylformamide. Methods using these reagents were tried with the dicyanoethyl derivatives. It was observed that with formaldehyde no reaction took place; with hexamine the formyl derivatives were formed in negligible amounts; with *N*-methylformanilide the yield was 40.7% with (I: R=H), 47% with (I: R=Me), and with dimethylformamide over 60% in both cases. These aldehydes after purification were characterised by the preparation of their semicarbazones, 2,4-DNP's, etc.

Further, these aldehydes were condensed with amino compounds like *p*-aminobenzoic acid, β -naphthylamine, and hydrazine and also with reactive methylene compounds like

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3046.

2. *Ibid.*, 1950, 3179.

3. Ferguson, *Chem. Rev.*, 1946, 38, 227.

malonic acid, diethyl malonate, malononitrile, ethyl cyanoacetate, and benzyl cyanide and with 2,4-dinitrotoluene.

It may also be mentioned that formylation of *N*-2'-cyanoethyl-*N*-methylaniline was also attempted. The yield of *p*-*N*-2'-cyanoethyl-*N*-methylanilino-benzaldehyde was, however, very small and the pure aldehyde could not be isolated. The 2,4-DNP of the aldehyde was prepared and identified.

EXPERIMENTAL

Formylation of NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaniline: Formation of p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde (II: R=H)

(a). *Using N-methylformanilide*.—A mixture of the dicyanoethylaniline (8.4 g.), *N*-methylformanilide (11.7 g.), POCl₃ (11.7 g.), and *o*-dichlorobenzene (7 ml) were taken in a r.b. flask fitted with an efficient mechanical stirrer and a reflux condenser. The mixture turned green with a copious evolution of HCl. After heating on a steam bath for 3 hours, the reddish, thick, oily liquid was cooled and crystalline sodium acetate (35 g.), dissolved in water (100 ml), was added. *o*-Dichlorobenzene and *N*-methylaniline were removed by steam distillation. The residual liquid on cooling deposited yellow needle-shaped crystals along with much resinous matter. After recrystallisation from ethanol, *p*-*NN*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde (3.8 g.) melted at 118°. (Found: C, 68.50; H, 6.20; N, 18.20. C₁₃H₁₃ON₂ requires C, 68.73; H, 5.73; N, 18.50%).

On increasing the heating period by 1 hour, the yield of the aldehyde was slightly improved. Longer heating, however, caused formation of more resinous matter and consequent loss in yield.

(b). *Using Dimethylformamide*.—To the dicyanoethylaniline (5.5 g.) were added POCl₃ (4.5 g.) and dimethylformamide (7.5 g.). The mixture after heating with stirring on a steam bath for 3 hours was poured slowly over crushed ice. A solution of crystalline sodium acetate (20 g.) in water (50 ml) was added to it and left overnight. Crystals of *p*-*NN*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde (3.8 g.) were obtained which after recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 118°.

The *semicarbazone* of the aldehyde was prepared in the usual manner and after recrystallisation from methanol it melted at 179°. (Found: N, 29.50. C₁₄H₁₅ON₆ requires N, 29.57%).

The 2,4-DNP of the aldehyde was obtained as deep red crystals, insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. It was purified by washing with hot ethanol and benzene; m.p. 251°. (Found: N, 23.99. C₁₉H₁₇O₄N₇ requires N, 24.08%).

The *azine* of the aldehyde was prepared by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde, hydrazine sulphate, and sodium carbonate in aqueous ethanol for 3 hours. The yield was almost quantitative. The pale yellow azine after recrystallisation from acetone melted at 220° and developed a deep red colour on moistening with HCl (conc.). (Found: N, 24.62. C₂₅H₂₆N₆ requires N, 24.88%).

Formylation of NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethyl-m-toluidine: Formation of 4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzaldehyde (II: R=Me)

The methods followed were the same as those described above. With *N*-methylformanilide, the yield of the aldehyde was about 47% and when dimethylformamide was used, it rose to 64%. The aldehyde after recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 148°. (Found: C, 69.80; H, 6.30; N, 17.40. $C_{14}H_{15}ON_3$ requires C, 69.71; H, 6.23; N, 17.42%).

The *semicarbazone* of the aldehyde, prepared in the usual manner and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, melted at 212°. (Found: N, 28.12. $C_{13}H_{18}ON_6$ requires N, 28.19%). The 2,4-DNP was obtained as deep red crystals, m.p. 234°. (Found: N, 22.99. $C_{20}H_{19}O_4N_7$ requires N, 23.28%).

The *azine* from the aldehyde, formed in the usual manner, was purified by recrystallisation from a large volume of acetone, m.p. 249°. (Found: N, 22.77. $C_{17}H_{16}N_8$ requires N, 23.46). The pale yellow crystal of the azine turned deep red when moistened with HCl (conc.).

Formylation of N-2'-Cyanoethyl-N-methylaniline using N-Methylformanilide

Formation of p-N-2'-Cyanoethyl-N-methylaminobenzaldehyde.—The usual procedure was adopted and the red resinous liquid was fractionally distilled at a reduced pressure. The viscous yellow fraction collected at 195–200°/21 mm was identified to be the aldehyde. This was confirmed by preparing the 2,4-DNP; m.p. 243°. (Found: N, 22.54. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_6$ requires N, 22.8%).

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-p'-aminobenzoic Acid.—An equimolecular mixture of the aldehyde (II: R=H) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid was dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethanol and then refluxed for 2 hours. The pale yellow product was recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 243°. The yield was poor, but it improved on using pyridine as a catalyst. (Found: N, 16.6. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_4$ requires N, 16.2%).

Attempts to condense the aldehyde with anthranilic and sulphanilic acids were unsuccessful.

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-β-naphthylamine.—Yellow glistening crystals (0.4 g.) were obtained by refluxing an ethanolic solution of the aldehyde (0.5 g.) and the amine (0.3 g.) for 2 hours. The compound was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 141°. (Found: N, 16.29. $C_{23}H_{20}N_4$ requires N, 15.90%).

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-2,4-dinitrotoluene.—Deep violet crystals of the compound in a good yield were obtained when a mixture of the aldehyde (0.75 g.), 2,4-dinitrotoluene (0.6 g.), and piperidine (2 drops) was heated on a steam bath for 30 minutes. Gummy matter formed during the reaction was removed by washing with hexane. It was then recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 206°. (Found: N, 17.86. $C_{20}H_{17}O_4N_5$ requires N, 17.90%).

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminocinnamic acid was prepared by the application of Robinson and Shinoda's method⁴. After 3 hours' heating on a water bath, the product was

extracted with a strong solution of sodium bicarbonate. The alkali extract on addition of excess of HCl (conc.) afforded a product, which melted with partial decomposition at 220-26°. This was probably due to the product being a mixture of cinnamic and the benzylidenemalonic acids. To ensure full conversion of the dibasic acid to the monobasic, the product was refluxed for 1 hour with excess of pyridine. The compound thus obtained was recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 233°, yield 51%. (Found: N, 15.30. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.64%). When piperidine alone was used as a condensing agent, the observations were the same.

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-ethyl Cyanoacetate.—A mixture of the aldehyde (1 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (0.5 g.), and piperidine (2 drops) was heated on a steam bath for 30 minutes. The mixture first melted but soon solidified. The yellow product was recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 169°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 17.28. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_4$ requires N, 17.39%).

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-malononitrile.—The aldehyde (0.7 g.), malononitrile (0.3 g.), ammonium acetate crystals (0.2 g.), and glacial acetic acid (1 ml) in dry benzene (15 ml) were taken in a flask fitted with a Dean-Stark constant water separator and refluxed for 15 minutes. The yellow crystals formed were filtered and recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 223°, yield 0.75 g. (Found: N, 25.20. $C_{16}H_{13}N_5$ requires N, 25.46%).

p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-ethyl Malonate.—A mixture of the aldehyde (1.1 g.), ethyl malonate (0.8 g.) and piperidine (2 drops) was heated on a steam bath for 24 hours. The solid product formed was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 117°, yield 0.8 g. (Found: N, 11.8. $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.4%). The yield of the product could be almost doubled when the period of heating (at 105°) was reduced to 12 hours.

p-NN'-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino- α -phenylcinnamonitrile.—The aldehyde (1g.) and benzyl cyanide (0.5 g.) were dissolved in ethanol (10 ml). Freshly prepared sodium ethoxide (10 mg.) was then added, the mixture stirred well for 10 minutes, and allowed to cool. The yellow solid product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 146°, yield 0.9 g. (Found: N, 17.30. $C_{21}H_{18}N_4$ requires N, 17.17%).

Attempts to condense the aldehyde with pentaerythrytol were unsuccessful.

Reactions of 4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzaldehyde

The aldehyde (II: R=Me) was condensed with β -naphthylamine, 2,4-dinitrotoluene, malonic acid, ethyl cyanoacetate, benzyl cyanide, and malononitrile. Attempts to condense it with *p*-aminobenzoic acid were unsuccessful. The methods employed in all these condensation reactions were the same as those described earlier. The following compounds were prepared.

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene- β -naphthylamine.— yield 81 %, m.p. 160°. (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{24}H_{22}N_4$ requires N, 15.3%).

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene-2,4-dinitrotoluene.—Yield 94%, m.p. 224°. (Found: N, 16.94. $C_{21}H_{19}O_4N_5$ requires N, 17.20%).

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylcinnamic Acid.—Yield 30.5%, m.p. 228°. (Found: N, 14.76. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.84%).

4-NN'-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene-ethyl Cyanoacetate.—Yield 42%, m.p. 194°. (Found: N, 16.2. $C_{19}H_{20}O_2N_4$ requires N, 16.6%)

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl- α -phenylcinnamionitrile.—Yield 61%, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 16.02. $C_{22}H_{20}N_4$ requires N, 16.47%).

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene-malonnitrile.—Yield 92%, m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 24.6. $C_{17}H_{15}N_3$ requires N, 24.2%).

Some attempts to condense this aldehyde with malonic ester and dibenzoylmethane were unsuccessful.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
ST. JOHN'S COLLEGE,
AGRA.

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